

A STUDY ON PROPERTIES OF BISMALLEIMIDE RESIN MODIFIED BY BENZOXAZINE FOR RTM PROCESS

Gang Liu*, Jianwen Bao

National Key Laboratory of Advanced Composites, Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, AVIC Composites Center, Beijing 100095, China
E-mail: liugang@iccas.ac.cn (Gang Liu)
baojianwen@hotmail.com (Jianwen Bao)

Keywords: Resin transfer molding (RTM), Bismaleimide (BMI) resin, Benzoxazine (BOZ), Low curing shrinkage

ABSTRACT

Bismaleimide (BMI) resin for resin transfer molding (RTM) process was modified by the benzoxazine (BOZ) with low curing shrinkage. The curing shrinkage, glass transition temperature and rheological properties of the BMI resin modified by different contents of BOZ were studied. The results show that the BMI resin modified by 7 phr BOZ exhibits excellent properties. Firstly, the curing shrinkage of the resin is decreased by about 16% due to modifier BOZ, relieving the apparent shrinkage cracks. In addition, the glass transition temperature of the BMI is decreased by the additive of BOZ. It may be explained by the fact that the BOZ decreases the density of rigid groups of the BMI molecule, which facilitates the segments movement, leading to a decline of the glass transition temperature. Finally, the curve of viscosity versus temperature for the modified resin indicates that the stage of low viscosity for RTM process is transferred towards lower temperature, with a longer processing period than that of the pure resin. Lower processing temperature and longer processing period for the resin are beneficial for the quality of the final composites component, considering good impregnation for the reinforcements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many outstanding advantages are endowed to composites such as high specific strength, good fatigue and corrosion resistance, easy to manufacture integral components with larger area, and to achieve structural-functional integrations. In recent years, advanced composites have been widely used in the aviation field and greatly improved the efficiency of advanced aircraft structure. The amount of composite materials used in aircrafts has become an important standard to assess the advancement of aircrafts [1-3]. However, the conventional autoclave molding process has high costs and energy consumptions, which restricts the application of composite materials to a certain extent. Hence, manufacturing technologies of composites with low costs are gradually on the rise. Resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) technologies as the representative of the liquid composite molding technology are the mainstream of research and development in this field at present [4-5]. As for foreign civil aircrafts, A380 and Boeing 787 aircrafts have been manufactured with extensive use of liquid composite molding technology to produce composite structures [6].

The primary factor for liquid composite molding technology, is to obtain a special resin with a particularly low initial viscosity and a long process period for processing. In recent time, there are series of liquid molding resin systems including epoxy, bismaleimide (BMI) resin and the like. Among these, bismaleimide resin has both good processing performances like epoxy and excellent high temperature performances like polyimide resin [7-9]. In addition, it also has good radiation resistance, good wet-heat aging resistance, excellent mechanical properties and outstanding electrical performances [10-11], resulting in widely applications in the fourth-generation fighters abroad [12]. However, BMI resin for RTM molding has small weight of the initial molecular to ensure lower viscosity for the injection, which can cause a series of problems, such as serious curing shrinkage in the molding process and a large interface residual stress between the resin matrix and the fiber, easily resulting in a decline of the matrix's strength or cracking, deflection, and dimensional instability. It

also leads to the invasion of oxygen, water and other environmental factors at the interface, which makes the materials easy to age and shorten their working life [13].

Benzoxazine resin, a new type of phenolic resins, maintains the traditional excellent heat resistance of phenolic resins and other advantages [14]. Further, due to the special structure, benzoxazine resin has a very small cure shrinkage [15]. Besides, the curing of benzoxazine resin is ring-opening polymerization and there is no small molecular by-products released during the curing process [16-17]. Moreover, low molecular weight and viscosity of the monomer and good solubility make it suitable for RTM process.

Therefore, in this paper, aromatic diamine benzoxazine resin with good compatibility of molecular structure and chemical reaction characteristics is employed as an inhibiting component for curing shrinkage. When this low cure shrinkage component is involved in the original curing reaction of BMI resin, it can reduce the curing shrinkage of the matrix resin significantly through the adjustment of crosslinked structure in the matrix resin. Therefore, the curing shrinkage is reduced on the basis of ensuring BMI resin processing performances and heat resistance.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Bismaleimide resin for RTM process is provided by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, China; Benzene and aromatic diamines oxazine (BOZ) resin is provided by College of polymer science and engineering, Sichuan University, China, whose molecular structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The molecular structure of aromatic diamine BOZ.

2.2 Preparation of modified resin system

Heat the RTM bismaleimide resin to 110 °C, then add BOZ to the resin and stir at a constant temperature of 110 °C until the mixture is uniform and transparent. The content of BOZ in the resin system is shown in Table 1.

Resin System	BOZ Content/phr
RTM resin 0#	0
Modified resin 1#	17
Modified resin 2#	7

Table 1: The contents of BOZ in resin system.

2.3 Preparation of resin casting body

Pour the mixed resin into the mold, then evacuate the air bubble for 30 minutes at 110 °C under the vacuum. Put the resin and the mold into the oven. The resin was cured with the process of 150 °C/1h+160 °C/1h+180 °C/2h+200 °C/8h.

2.4 Test instruments and conditions

Rheometer: TA Instruments AR2000, the heating rate is 3 °C/min, RT~200 °C.

Dynamic thermomechanical analysis (DMA): TA Instruments Q800 DMA with double cantilever beam clamp, the heating rate is 5 °C/min, RT~350 °C.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Rheological properties of the modified resin

Figure 2 shows the rheological properties of the pure BMI resin and that of two modified ones. The temperature range where the viscosity of 0# resin is lower than 1Pa·s is 89 °C~168 °C, and the temperature range where it is lower than 300 mPa·s is 105 °C~165 °C. The temperature range where the viscosity of 1# resin is lower than 1Pa·s is 92 °C~158 °C, and the temperature range where it is lower than 300 mPa·s is 107 °C~152 °C. The temperature range where the viscosity of 2# resin is lower than 1Pa·s is 68 °C~153 °C, and the temperature range where it is lower than 300 mPa·s is 81 °C~149 °C. The results show that the low-viscosity temperature ranges of both the modified resin with different contents of BOZ shift to lower temperature. The BMI resin used in this study is composed of 4, 4'-diaminodiphenyl methane double maleicimide (BDM) and diallylbisphenol A (BA), in whose curing process the etherification happens [18], as shown in Figure 3. While in the modified resin system, the double bond of BDM and BOZ react, forming the hydroxyl. The etherification is easy to happen at a relatively low temperature for these hydroxyls [19]. It may be attributed to the fact that there is no obvious steric effect for the hydroxyl after the ring-opening of BOZ, which leads the hydroxyl and the double bond of BDM to react easily, as shown in Figure 4. So the gel reaction in modified resin system take place at a relatively low temperature, and the low-viscosity temperature ranges shift to lower temperature on the viscosity-temperature curve.

Figure 1: Testing results of the rheological properties for the resin system.

Figure 2: The etherification of BDM and BA.

Figure 3: The etherification of BDM and BOZ.

3.2 Glass transition temperature

The DMA curves of the three types of resins are shown in Figure 5. The glass transition temperatures of 0#, 1# and 2#, based on $\tan\delta$ curves, are 273 °C, 251 °C and 223 °C, respectively. From the results, it can be seen that the glass transition temperature is decreased by about 50 °C due to the modification. Since BMI resin contains benzene and imide heterocyclic structure, it shows a high crosslinking density, presenting an excellent thermo-tolerance property. After modified by BOZ, the rigid group ratio in BMI is reduced, facilitating the motivation of chain segments and resulting in the decrease of glass transition temperature.

Figure 5: The DMA curves of modified resins with different amounts of BOZ: 0# (a), 1# (b) and 2# (c).

3.3 Curing shrinkage characteristics

1# resin with higher amount of BOZ shows short stage of low viscosity, implying a deficient manufacturability for large scale composites structures via RTM process. Hence, in this work, 2# resin is selected to investigate the effects of BOZ addition on the curing shrinkage characteristics of BMI.

The curves of the volume changing with temperature for the pure resin and 2# resin during the curing process are shown in Figure 6 and Table 2. $\Delta V1$ is the maximum expanding volume per weight in heat-up process; $\Delta V2$ is the volume change per weight between uncured and cured states at room temperature; $\Delta V3$ is the volume change per weight when cool down from injection temperature to room temperature and negative values correspond to the volume decrease.

Indicated by the data in Table 2, the pure resin presents the highest value of $\Delta V1$, which means it undergoes larger volume expansion under the same processing conditions. This phenomenon may lead to a larger volume shrinkage after curing process, as larger volume expansion means higher pressure in mould.

The $\Delta V2$ of modified resin decreases by 16% approximately when compared to the pure one. The phenomenon can be attributed to the following two reasons. On the one hand, thermoset resins generally show volume shrinkage when cured, because the Van der Waals force between monomers transfers to covalent bonds during crosslinking process. When it comes to BOZ, its curing reaction belongs to ring-opening polymerization. It is well-known that, in ring-opening polymerization, there must be covalent bonds transferred to Van der Waals force, while Van der Waals force is transferred to covalent bonds. Thereby, the shrinkage and expansion of BOZ produced during the curing process can be partially offset. On the other hand, as sufficient hydrogen bonds intra- and inter- BOZ molecules, its excellent structure enhances the rigidity of the molecular chains, restrains the molecule packing and generates more free volume, resulting in no volume shrinkage during the curing process [20-21].

Generally speaking, resin is injected into the mould at processing temperature and then cooled down to room temperature after curing process, so $\Delta V3$ is more practical for the investigation of RTM process. As shown in Table 2, the $\Delta V3$ of modified resin decreases by about 36% compared to the pure one. Besides, a smoother surface morphology of the modified resin can be seen in Figure 7, suggesting a better usability.

Figure 6: Volume change with temperature during the curing process for 0# (a) and 2# (b).

	ΔV_1 / $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	ΔV_2 / $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	ΔV_3 / $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$
0#	0.0677	-0.0248	-0.0574
2#	0.0656	-0.0209	-0.0370

Table 2: Volume change during the curing process.

Figure 7: Photographs of the cured resin for 0# (a) and 2# (b).

4 CONCLUSIONS

In order to decrease the curing shrinkage of Bismaleimide (BMI) resin, used for RTM process, we designed a benzoxazine (BOZ) resin to modify the BMI. By adding different contents of BOZ to the BMI resin, the modified BMI were prepared. It was found that the BMI modified by 7phr BOZ exhibits excellent comprehensive performances. The curing shrinkage of the modified BMI is decreased by about 16%. For the thermal behavior, the stage of low viscosity of the modified BMI is transferred towards lower temperature, with a longer processing period than that of the pure resin. The modified resin shows good processibility for RTM, though the glass transfer temperature is slightly decreased.

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